

IMPROVING COMPUTER SIMULATION OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS AND FLOTATION EQUIPMENT IN THE PRODUCTION OF POTASH FERTILIZER

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Annotation This article discusses the improvement of computer modeling of the technological process and flotation apparatus in the production of potash fertilizer.

Keyword: model, computer, modeling, system, analysis, equipment, production, technology, process, flotation.

The use of computer modeling in the modernization and creation of processing equipment is playing an increasingly important role in the development of the mining industry.

In modern science, the most important concept has appeared - a system. It first appeared in cybernetics. And it makes it possible to realize the creation of a mathematical model, the objects being studied, and large generalizations with the identification of new patterns. Based on systems thinking and analysis, computer modeling and optimization of the technological process of flotation as a complex technological production, we can assume the improvement of theory and practice [1]. The study of production products and their production is implemented in sequence: first stage - analytical inference and study;

- First of all, a certain industrial production and its components are studied. Requirements for production and its departments are being developed;
- in each production, many technological processes can take place, from which those that are necessary to achieve the set goals are selected in advance.

- Determination of optimal technological production parameters and their mutual influence in the processes of the system. In this case, the production links are also determined. With presence, you can implement tasks without taking into account the process;

- The production under study consists of different elements, for each selected element its technological parameters, etc. are specified. Adjustment of a link and its subdivision into further links is not limited. It is implemented in necessary cases and when it is appropriate to study for the implementation of optimal solutions [1].

Second phase. Finding the mutual influence of indicators. Depending on the type of object and the problem being solved, each research scientist can use a large stock of methods from the industry where the study is being carried out. Finding the mass ratio of indicators leads to the use of mathematical formulas, which can lead to the use of mathematical or computer models.

Third stage. The selection of the required project at this stage is clarified and adjusted in accordance with the requirements of standards and technical specifications and the study of systems. A selection of criteria is made for the primary link and for sub-links of all levels. A method for finding the optimal system is being selected. This solution is being implemented.

Stage 1 - the beginning of the study of the results of the analysis, which is suitable for all branches of science. Analytical inference helps in the analysis of many sciences. The implementation of the 2nd and 3rd stages is carried out depending on the task. Based on a systems approach, the obtained data from a system study influences the researcher's thought process and the subsequent decision is more effective [1].

On this basis and the solution to the problem of computer algorithmization of the technological process of flotation in the production of potash fertilizer suggests:

- development of systems thinking in the field of algorithms for modeling and improving the flotation complex apparatus in the production of potash fertilizer, analysis of objects and optimization of physical and chemical enrichment operations,

determination of optimal parameters for the transition of valuable reagents into the gas component of flotation;

- improvement of methods for studying systems of the process of beneficiation of natural ores;
- creation of methods for analytical control of a dynamic model of the ore enrichment process;
- creation of multi-stage methods for modeling production processes for producing potash fertilizer using computer and digital technologies and improving the flotation complex apparatus in the production of potash fertilizer and on this basis solving problems of technological optimization and synthesis of effective optimal calculation systems;
- justification of the methodology for calculating the optimal parameters of the dynamics of the technological process;
- justification of the methodology for calculating the optimal parameters of the dynamic process and the creation of optimal operating conditions for the flotation complex.

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